

1 **Molecular phylogeny and diversity of the Corsican red-legged partridge:**
2 **containing genetic homogenization in the species**

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10 Short title: Genetic analysis of the Corsican red-legged partridge

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27 **Abstract.** The red-legged partridge, *Alectoris rufa* (Phasianidae), is a game bird hunted
28 throughout its range (Italy, France with Corsica island, Iberian Peninsula). The release
29 in the wild of farmed birds of unknown origin coupled to the hybridization with the
30 exotic chukar (*A. chukar*: East Mediterranean to East Asia) led to the reduction of the
31 spatial component of genetic variability and to the pollution of *A. rufa*, respectively. On
32 mainland, *A. chukar* genes occur according to an Italy-to-Iberian Peninsula decreasing
33 gradient. However, Corsica hosts a number of *A. rufa* x *A. chukar* hybrids much lower
34 than nearby Italy. We investigated kinship and diversity of Corsican *A. rufa* to aid
35 management decisions aimed at containing genetic homogenization in this species. We
36 sampled 97 red-legged partridges in four regions of Corsica with different habitat (semi-
37 arid: Desertu di l'Agriate; rural: Nessa-Felicetu; mountainous: Vivariu-Venacu and
38 Fium'Orbu-Taravu). A subset ($n = 60$) was sequenced at the mitochondrial DNA
39 (mtDNA) Cytochrome-*b* and compared with 105 samples collected in the continental
40 part of the *A. rufa* range. Corsican samples were also genotyped at eight loci of the
41 microsatellite DNA to infer intraspecific relationships at a finer scale. We also used
42 microsatellite data from a previous study to compare *A. rufa* reared in the only island
43 farm with wild conspecifics of this work. Corsican partridges grouped in the only
44 statistically reliable and diverging mtDNA clade. Microsatellites provided evidence for
45 the genetic isolation of Fium'Orbu-Taravu mountain *A. rufa* population, whose low
46 level of hybridization with *A. chukar* had been already unveiled. We found that released
47 captive partridges did not enter the wild breeding populations. We suggested banning *A.*
48 *rufa* translocation from Corsica to the continent to comply with the disclosed genetic
49 kinship, and *viceversa* to contrast the spreading of *A. chukar* pollution.

50

51 **Keywords:** *Alectoris rufa*; *Alectoris chukar*; conservation management; chukar;
52 invasive genotypes; island population biology; microsatellite DNA; mitochondrial DNA

53 **Introduction**

54 Island bird populations are of evolutionary interest as local selective pressures often
55 lead to allopatric speciation (Grant & Grant, 2002). Among game birds, however,
56 management may work against the preservation of island population genetic
57 distinctiveness (Frankham, Ballou & Briscoe, 2002). Introduction of wildlife through
58 restocking plans may allow the hybridization between formerly separated gene pools
59 (*sensu* Short, 1969; cf., Rhymer & Simberloff, 1996) and, as a result, lead to the rising
60 of genetic homogenization (Olden *et al.*, 2004).

61 The red-legged partridge, *Alectoris rufa* (Phasianidae), is a medium-sized game bird
62 hunted throughout its distribution range, which extends from the North West Italy
63 across France (with Corsica) to the Iberian Peninsula. Three subspecies are recognised
64 on a morphological basis: *A. r. rufa* in Italy and France (with Corsica), *A. r. intercedens*
65 in South and East Spain (also Balearics), and *A. r. hispanica* in Portugal and North West
66 Spain (Fig. 1) (Madge & McGowan, 2002). Anthropogenic hybridization with the
67 exotic chukar partridge (*Alectoris chukar*: East Mediterranean to East Asia) represents a
68 major threatening factor to the conservation of *A. rufa*. In captivity the chukar is the
69 most prolific *Alectoris* breeder, and crossing with red-legged partridges is productive
70 for farmers. In the absence of genetic control, looking like pure yet real hybrid red-
71 legged partridges (e.g., high-category backcrosses to *A. rufa*) are released to sustain
72 wild populations. As a result, nowadays a deep genetic pollution occurs in the entire *A.*
73 *rufa* range (Barbanera *et al.*, 2005; Barilani *et al.*, 2007).

74 Barbanera *et al.* (2010) investigated *A. rufa* diversity using the Cytochrome-*b* gene
75 (Cyt-*b*) of mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA). They found that, on mainland, *A. chukar*
76 genes occurred according to an Italy-to-Iberian Peninsula decreasing gradient. Although
77 no *A. chukar* haplotype was found in Corsica, using nuclear DNA markers Barbanera *et*
78 *al.* (2010) found that Corsica hosted a number of *A. rufa* x *A. chukar* hybrids. This

79 latter, however, was much lower than in nearby Italy (cf., Barbanera *et al.*, 2005).

80 The island of Corsica is essentially an isolated mountain with herringbone granite
81 peaks extending from North West to South East (e.g. Mount Cinto, 2706 m: Fig. 1). It
82 represents a valuable model system in studies aimed at comparing insular vs. European
83 mainland communities. The first evidence for the introduction of *A. rufa* in Corsica
84 backs to the sixth century BC, but origin of founders is unknown and older colonizing
85 events cannot be excluded (Vigne, Bailon & Cuisin, 1997). In this study, we
86 investigated the molecular kinship and diversity of Corsican *A. rufa* populations of
87 different habitats in order to aid management decisions aimed at containing genetic
88 homogenization in this species.

89

90 **Materials and methods**

91

92 **Study area**

93 Study area mirrors the composite habitat assemblage typical to Corsica. In the northern
94 part of the island, we investigated *A. rufa* in a semi-arid coastal district (Desertu di
95 l'Agriate, DA, 0-600 m) as well as in a rural area of the Balagna region (Nessa-Felicetu,
96 NF, 300-600 m). We also investigated *A. rufa* in two inner mountain districts (Vivariu-
97 Venacu, VV, 1000-2000 m; Fium'Orbu-Taravu, FT, 1300-2000 m) (Fig. 1). Overall, the
98 study area is subject to fires, scarcely populated by humans and extensively used for
99 bovine and caprine livestock-breeding. Mediterranean cultivations (vineyards, olive
100 groves) are essentially restricted to the NF area (Gamisans, 1991). Chestnut groves and
101 hazel characterize the mountain districts (VV, FT), which harbour *A. rufa* populations
102 never supplemented with captive-bred specimens (Pietri *et al.*, 2004). These populations
103 are comprised within the limits of the Natural Regional Park of Corsica, whereas there
104 are no protected areas in the NF and DA regions.

105 The average density of Corsican *A. rufa* stands at about 1 pair/Km². However, this
106 value grows up to 2.6 - 5 pair/Km² in the North West (including NF area) because of
107 frequent restocking activity (Birkan, 1990). Although *A. rufa* is hunted across the whole
108 Corsica, in the North West the species faces with the highest pressure. The only
109 operating *A. rufa* island farm located in Carbuccia (Fig. 1) imports 30% of its birds from
110 the French mainland. Barbanera *et al.* (2009) proved that this captive population is
111 deeply *A. chukar*-introgressed.

112

113 **Biological sampling**

114 We obtained 97 samples from hunted red-legged partridges of wild Corsican
115 populations inhabiting the aforementioned regions (Fig. 1, Table 1). Only one sample
116 (liver) for each hunting trip was collected to prevent risk of genotyping birds of the
117 same covey. We also collected 105 *A. rufa* samples in the Iberian Peninsula, France and
118 Italy (Table 1). Samples were all 95% ethanol preserved at - 40 °C.

119

120 **DNA extraction**

121 We extracted DNA from all samples using the Puregene Core Kit-A (Qiagen) following
122 the manufacturer's instructions. The DNA content was determined with an Eppendorf
123 BioPhotometer (AG Eppendorf).

124

125 **Mitochondrial DNA**

126 We amplified 1092 bp of *Cyt-b* as in Barbanera *et al.* (2005), a portion of the gene
127 much longer than that used by Barbanera *et al.* (2010) (1092 vs. 229 bp in $n = 60$ vs. $n =$
128 48 specimens, respectively). We purified PCR products using the GenElute PCR Clean-
129 up Kit (volume, 40 μ l; Sigma Aldrich). The sequencing was performed (165 sequences:
130 60 from Corsica and 105 from the mainland range of *A. rufa*) in both directions on an

131 ABI 3730 DNA automated sequencer at Genechron (Rome, Italy).

132 Bayesian phylogenetic analysis with Metropolis-coupled Markov chain Monte Carlo
133 algorithms was conducted using MRBAYES (v. 3.1.2: Huelsenbeck & Ronquist, 2001).
134 We used MRMODELTEST (v. 2.3: Nylander, 2004), a simplified version of MODELTEST (v.
135 3.06: Posada & Crandall, 1998), and PAUP* (v. 4.0b10: Swofford, 2002) to estimate the
136 best substitution model fitting to our mtDNA dataset. According to the Akaike
137 Information Criterion (AIC; Posada & Buckley, 2004), we selected the HKY85
138 (Hasegawa, Kishino & Yano, 1985) + I model ($-\ln L = 1961.3$; $AIC = 3932.5$; $I = 0.63$;
139 $T_i/T_v = 9.96$). We applied the selected evolutionary model with parameters estimated
140 during the analysis. Two independent runs of analysis were conducted for 6 000 000
141 generations with a sample frequency of 100 (four chains, heating = 0.2, random starting
142 tree). Convergence between the two runs was monitored in MRBAYES through the
143 standard deviation of split frequencies, and runs were continued until this value dropped
144 to 0.0022. We monitored with TRACER the convergence of each run towards stationarity
145 (v. 1.4: Rambaud & Drummond, 2007), which was reached after 1 200 000 generations
146 (i.e., 12 000 trees were discarded as burn-in); 96 002 trees were used to produce 50%
147 majority-rule consensus trees with PAUP*.

148 Neighbour Joining (NJ: Saitou & Nei, 1987) and Maximum Parsimony (MP:
149 Swofford *et al.*, 1996) methods were also used to infer phylogenetic relationships using
150 PAUP*. The NJ tree was constructed with the HKY85 + I model (selected by MODELTEST
151 with AIC), while the MP procedure was as in Barbanera *et al.* (2007). All trees were
152 rooted using a rock partridge (*Alectoris graeca*, GenBank accession code: AM850716).
153 While the posterior probability (PP) values were calculated through the Bayesian
154 analysis, in the NJ and MP reconstructions the statistical support for each node was
155 evaluated by bootstrapping (BP) (10 000 replicates: Felsenstein, 1985). Only
156 statistically well-supported clades were taken into account ($PP \geq 0.99$, for Bayesian

157 analysis: Erixon *et al.*, 2003; BP \geq 70%, for NJ and MP: Hillis & Bull, 1993).

158 We carried out haplotype network using the Median Joining method (Bandelt,
159 Forster & Röhl, 1999) with NETWORK (v. 4.5.1.0, © 2004-2009 Fluxus Technology).
160 We used MEGA (v. 4.1: Kumar *et al.*, 2008) with the TN93 algorithm (Tamura & Nei,
161 1993) to compute the average genetic distance ($d \pm SE$, standard error; 1000 replicates)
162 between the Corsican population and the three *A. rufa* subspecies (Table 1). Haplotype
163 diversity ($h \pm SD$, standard deviation, only for the Corsican population as whole) was
164 computed with DNASP (v. 5.1: Librado & Rozas, 2009). We deposited haplotype
165 sequences in GenBank (accession codes: FN689441-FN689466).

166

167 **Microsatellite DNA**

168 We used the same microsatellite (Short Tandem Repeats, STR) dataset of Barbanera *et*
169 *al.* (2010) obtained through the genotyping of 97 Corsican partridges (Table 1) at eight
170 STR loci isolated from chicken (*Gallus gallus*) and *A. rufa* genome (Gonzalez, Castilla
171 & Zardoya, 2005; Barilani *et al.*, 2007: Table 3). PCR reactions (12.5 μ l) contained 10
172 ng of DNA, 2 mM MgCl₂, 2 mM dNTP, 0.6 μ M of each primer, 1X PCR Gold buffer
173 and 0.3 U/ μ l AmpliTaq Gold DNA Polymerase (Applied Biosystems). Thermal profile
174 was: (94 °C for 2 min) + [(94 °C for 45 s) + (T_M for 45 s + (72 °C for 1 min)] x 5 cycles
175 + [(94 °C for 45 s) + (T_M for 45 s) + (72 °C for 1 min)] x 25 cycles + 72 °C for 10 min
176 (T_M, annealing temperature: Table 3).

177 We used GENEPOP (v. 3.4: Raymond & Rousset, 1995) and ARLEQUIN (v. 3.5.1:
178 Excoffier, Laval & Schneider, 2005) to calculate expected ($H_{E,}$) and observed
179 heterozygosity ($H_{O,}$), to infer deviations from Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium (HWE) and
180 Linkage Disequilibrium (LE), and to calculate the gene flow ($N_e m$, effective number of
181 migrants per generation) via the private allele method of Slatkin (1985). The
182 significance level of HWE and LE tests was estimated using the Bonferroni correction

183 (Hochberg, 1988). We investigated the partition of the STR diversity among
184 populations and among individuals within populations, using AMOVA (Analysis of
185 molecular variance) and Wright's (1951) F -statistics (10 000 permutations) with the
186 program ARLEQUIN.

187 Principal Component Analyses (PCAs) were applied as an exploratory tool for
188 investigating the major patterns of genetic variability. We plotted the F_{ST} distance values
189 on the axes of PCAs using the program STATISTICA 5.0/W (Statsoft Inc., USA). First, we
190 used the STR loci (MCW 104, MCW 118, MCW, 280, Aru 1.23, Aru 1.27) shared by
191 the study of Barbanera *et al.* (2009: for Carbuccia farmed population) and the present
192 one (for DA, NF, VV and FT wild populations). Then, we performed another PCA with
193 all STR loci including only the wild populations of this study.

194

195 **Results**

196

197 **Mitochondrial DNA**

198 The real mitochondrial nature of our Cyt-*b* sequences was confirmed through the
199 comparison with those obtained from isolated mtDNA, hence, any potential occurrence
200 of Numts (mitochondrial sequences of nuclear origin) was excluded (see Barbanera *et*
201 *al.*, 2005). The alignment (with outgroup) included 71 variables sites. Of these, 14 were
202 parsimony informative. We found 26 *A. rufa* haplotypes (H). Of these, seven were
203 found in the Corsican partridges (three private: H5, H6 and H7). Bayesian, NJ, and MP
204 (length, 98; consistency index, 0.857; retention index, 0.650) procedures concurrently
205 clustered the 92% of the Corsican representatives ($n = 55$, all populations) in the only
206 statistically very well supported clade (Fig. 2: Bayesian, 0.99; NJ, 92%; MP, 94%). Two
207 more clades were not significantly supported (Fig. 2, upper *: Bayesian, 0.90; NJ, 58%;
208 MP, 60%; lower *: Bayesian, 0.83; NJ, 64%; MP, 64%). The network (Fig. 2: inset)

209 confirmed the results produced by the phylogenetic reconstructions. Haplotype 3 was
210 the most frequent (23%) among those distributed across the entire range of the red-
211 legged partridge. The 88% of Corsican specimens hold haplotype 1, the only one found
212 in the FT population, which was shared merely with partridges from the French
213 mainland. Haplotype H1 was separated from H3 by three mutational changes: two in 3rd
214 (A - G transitions, position No. 390 and No. 693: Randi, 1996) and one in 1st codon
215 position (T - C transition, with Phenylalanine - Leucine aminoacidic change, position
216 No. 718: Randi, 1996). Haplotype diversity ($h \pm SD$) computed for the entire Corsican
217 population was 0.25 ± 0.07 , while the average distance versus each *A. rufa* subspecies
218 ranged between 0.22% and 0.35% (Table 2).

219

220 **Microsatellite DNA**

221 All eight loci were polymorphic with the exception of MCW 118 (excluded from the
222 analysis: Table 3). All Corsican populations were at HWE with the exception of FT,
223 which showed a significant deficiency of heterozygotes (Fisher test, $P < 0.001$). The LE
224 test carried out for all pairs of loci did not disclose any linked loci.

225 When the Carbuccia farm population was compared with the wild *A. rufa* of this
226 study (five STR loci: see Materials and methods), the F_{ST} value obtained by AMOVA
227 was 0.10 ($P < 0.001$; variability among populations: 10.0%; variability among
228 individuals within populations: 90.0%). In the relative PCA plot, we found that the
229 Carbuccia population was strongly separated with respect to all the wild ones of this
230 study (Fig. 3: white circles; see also Table 4). When the entire set of STR loci was used
231 to investigate only the wild *A. rufa* of this study, the F_{ST} value obtained by AMOVA
232 was 0.04 ($P < 0.001$; variability among populations: 4.39%; variability among
233 individuals within populations: 95.61%). Most of the Corsican populations were
234 significantly differentiated (Table 4). When the F_{ST} distance values were plotted on the

235 first two axes of a PCA (Fig. 3: black circles), the first two components explained
236 98.3% of the STR diversity and marked out the divergence especially of the FT
237 population. Finally, the gene flow among farmed and wild Corsican populations was
238 reported in Table 4.

239

240 **Discussion**

241

242 **Genetic kinship within *A. rufa***

243 Phylogenetic reconstructions did not reveal any correspondence between the three
244 known *A. rufa* subspecies (Table 1) and the mtDNA clades (Fig. 2). However, the
245 Corsican clade was the only one with very robust statistical support concurrently
246 obtained with all methods (Bayesian, Neighbour-Joining and Maximum Parsimony).
247 The large majority of Corsican partridges showed the same haplotype (H1), and the
248 genetic distance versus *A. rufa* conspecifics inhabiting the mainland Europe was lower
249 than 0.35% (Table 2). Taking into account that the Corsican haplotype 1 is shared only
250 by conspecifics from the Department of Gard (South France: Fig. 2), and that the
251 frequency of H1 is very high in both VV and FT wild populations (i.e., those never
252 supplemented through restocking plans: Pietri *et al.*, 2004), we concluded that *A. rufa*
253 was likely introduced from France to Corsica. Our mtDNA dataset pointed against the
254 past description of *Caccabis rufa corsa* (*A. rufa corsa*) as fourth subspecies (Parrot,
255 1910) and confirmed its synonymy with *A. rufa rufa*. The average genetic distance
256 value computed among the three *A. rufa* subspecies (*c.* 0.1%: Table 2) was ten time
257 smaller than that disclosed by Randi *et al.* (2003) in the rock partridge (*c.* 1%: *A. graeca*
258 *saxatilis*, *A. g. orlandoi* and *A. g. graeca* subspecies), even excluding the Sicilian *A. g.*
259 *whitakeri* (a Pleistocene relict population). In *A. rufa*, the management to
260 counterbalance hunting drawings and the related commerce of eggs/chicks is much

261 more intense than in *A. graeca*. This has likely contributed to the reduction of the spatial
262 component of *A. rufa* genetic variability during last 150 years (Barbanera *et al.*, 2010).

263

264 **Diversity of Corsican *A. rufa***

265 Recently Spanò (2010) stressed the small contribution of supplementation through
266 restocking plans to the steadiness of the *A. rufa* population in Corsica. Between 1979
267 and 2008, released captive-bred partridges (3000 - 5000 birds/year) were much less than
268 those usually hunted (15 000 - 18 000 birds/year). The lack of *A. rufa* haplotypes shared
269 between farmed (Barbanera *et al.*, 2009) and wild (this study) Corsican red-legged
270 partridge reinforced the concern about the efficiency of the only operating island farm
271 (located in Carbuccia: Fig. 1). Then again, despite the *A. chukar*-introgressed status of
272 the Carbuccia population (Barbanera *et al.*, 2009), we did not find any *A. chukar*
273 haplotype in the wild partridges of the island. Similarly, the PCA plot obtained using
274 the F_{ST} distance values computed on the basis of STR genotyping (Fig. 3: white
275 circles), strongly pointed against any tight relationships between wild and farmed *A.*
276 *rufa* of Corsica. All these evidences suggest that released captive-bred birds did not
277 apparently enter the wild populations (Table 4). Hence, it seems that the introduction of
278 exotic genotypes could have not occurred in very recent times. Nonetheless, RAPDs
279 disclosed *A. rufa* x *A. chukar* hybrids in all Corsican populations (Barbanera *et al.*,
280 2010). A probable explanation to this discrepancy between mitochondrial (lack of both
281 *A. rufa* and *A. chukar* haplotypes of farm origin in the wild) and nuclear (presence of *A.*
282 *rufa* x *A. chukar* hybrids in the wild) DNA results is that severe bottlenecks (especially
283 in an island) can erase mtDNA haplotypes while retaining nuclear DNA introgression.
284 Whereas the disappearance of the *A. rufa* (or *A. chukar*) haplotypes may occur even
285 within a single generation (through the mating even with *A. rufa* x *A. chukar* hybrids
286 proved they hold the *A. rufa* mtDNA lineage), the dilution of *A. chukar* loci within the

287 *A. rufa* genome (through the mating with pure *A. rufa*) would need many more
288 generations (cf., Barbanera *et al.*, 2007).

289 The Fium'Orbu-Taravu (FT) population showed only one mtDNA haplotype (H1:
290 Fig. 2). This population was the only showing heterozygote deficiency, whereas the
291 others were in Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium (Table 3). Fium'Orbu-Taravu is an inner,
292 isolated mountain region characterized by very changeable weather conditions during
293 winter, especially in terms of snow cover. It is feasible that in the past successive
294 bottlenecks allowed the loss of genetic variability in the Corsican *A. rufa*. As
295 exhaustively discussed by Cristescu *et al.* (2010), however, the number of STRs used in
296 this work did not allow testing this hypothesis in a reliable way. Similarly, the very few
297 mtDNA haplotypes found in each Corsican population hindered any demographic
298 inference. On the other hand, the single population datasets could be not pooled together
299 because of the genetic structure unveiled by STRs (see below).

300 In contrast to the mtDNA, the STRs provided evidence of both isolated and
301 connected Corsican populations of different habitats. This result did not come as a
302 surprise. In this study the apportionment of the genetic diversity was larger by STR than
303 by mtDNA loci, but the opposite may occur as well (e.g.: Borden & Stepien, 2006). The
304 AMOVA revealed highly significant partition of the STR diversity among populations
305 and among individuals within populations (Table 4). For instance, the F_{ST} distance
306 values showed highly significant divergence between the southernmost (FT) and the
307 northern populations (Fig. 1, Table 4). More in general, the most likely explanation for
308 the discordance between mtDNA and STR in detecting the population genetic structure
309 is that mtDNA genetics is determined by an effective population size (N_e) that is 1/4 as
310 large as that of nuclear DNA. STRs have a higher mutation rate than mtDNA, but they
311 would need thousands of generations to accumulate the same amount of genetic
312 difference in isolated populations (Birky, Maruyama & Fuerst, 1983).

313 Many assumptions are involved in the estimate of the gene flow and results must be
314 always taken with extreme care (Allendorf & Luikart, 2007). In Corsica, the highest
315 value of gene flow was found between NF and DA populations (Table 4: $N_e m = 4.2$).
316 Given their closeness and the lack of geographic barriers, such a result could be
317 expected. On the contrary, the high level of gene flow detected between DA and VV
318 populations (Table 4: $N_e m = 3.7$) deserves a comment. These populations inhabit the
319 extremes of the central depression of Corsica (70-80 Km: Fig. 1), which, in turn,
320 harbours North West to South West stretching sedimentary basins including the
321 Ostriconi, Golo and Tavignano river valleys. Overall, this area offers suitable habitat to
322 *A. rufa* (olive groves, uncultivated areas and open grounds). Although *A. rufa* is a
323 sedentary species (Cramp & Simmons, 1980), it is truthful that NF, DA and VV
324 populations were connected across the central depression much more than
325 geographically closer mountain populations could be (e.g. VV and FT: Fig. 1, Table 4).
326 Such a depression would act as a North-South ecological corridor. Not only
327 geographical and geological (Reille *et al.*, 1997) but also biological evidences hold up
328 this hypothesis. Falchi *et al.* (2009) investigated the Corsican *Cistus creticus*, an
329 important evergreen shrub of the island maquis. They sequenced chloroplast DNA and
330 found that populations living at the extremes of the central depression were
331 phylogenetically tightly related yet both diverging versus those of South Corsica.
332 Likewise, Faggio, Cart & Jolin (2009) found that young red kites (*Milvus milvus*,
333 Accipitridae) leaving the breeding sites of the Balagna region usually move along the
334 central depression to winter roosts located between Saint Florent (in the North) and
335 Poggio di Venacu (in the South).

336

337 **Management suggestions to contain genetic homogenization**

338 Management of a given population aims to keep genetic options alive for future

339 adaptation (Reid & Miller, 1989). This is a very hard task in *A. rufa* due to the intense
340 management and to the genetic pollution with *A. chukar*. The island of Corsica is not an
341 exception and is known to harbour both captive (Barbanera *et al.*, 2009) and wild
342 (Barbanera *et al.*, 2010) *A. rufa* x *A. chukar* hybrid populations. However, wild
343 Corsican *A. rufa* (except NF) hold a degree of hybridization with *A. chukar* lower than
344 that disclosed in nearby mainland Europe (Barbanera *et al.*, 2005, 2010).

345 Conservation management of hybrid populations is a controversial issue as “nearly
346 every situation involving hybridization is different enough that general rules are not
347 likely to be effective” (Allendorf *et al.*, 2001). In *A. rufa*, hybridization occurs with
348 widespread introgression (hybrid swarm: Allendorf & Luikart, 2007). Hence, any
349 eradication of hybrids would be ineffective even at a regional scale. We realize that
350 efforts should focus on protecting the remaining, if any, pure *A. rufa* populations.
351 Nonetheless, given the high demand of birds by hunters, some guidelines to manage
352 hybrid populations are necessary to avoid the genetic chaos to which otherwise *A. rufa*
353 would be destined, especially in the easternmost part of its range.

354 The island of Corsica hosts the only genetically homogeneous and diverging *A. rufa*
355 population. We advocate the ban of *A. rufa* translocation from Corsica to the continent
356 to comply with disclosed intraspecific genetic kinship, and *viceversa* to contain
357 spreading of the *A. chukar* pollution. The Fium’Orbu-Taravu (FT) mountain population
358 is that of major conservation interest in Corsica because of its genetic (Fig. 3; Table 4)
359 and geographical (Fig. 1; see Materials and methods) isolation. This latter is warranted
360 by the occurrence of a large woodland area (Vizzavona Forest) between Vivariu-
361 Venacu and Fium’Orbu-Taravu regions that partridges cannot pass through. Moreover,
362 the FT population is also *A. chukar*-polluted at a lower extent than nearby populations
363 (Barbanera *et al.*, 2010). We encourage the monitoring of the FT population to set up
364 harvesting on reliable data. We suggest the complete renewal of the highly *A. chukar*-

365 introgressed captive population of Carbuccia farm (Barbanera *et al.*, 2009; Fig. 1), and
366 consequent short-time ban of *A. rufa* releases in the entire Corsica. Finally, new *ex-situ*
367 founders, hopefully drawn from the FT population, should be genetically identified
368 through available nuclear DNA markers (microsatellites, RAPDs and Single Nucleotide
369 Polymorphisms: Barilani *et al.*, 2007; Barbanera *et al.*, 2010; Sevane *et al.*, 2010).

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384

385 **References**

386 Allendorf, F.W. & Luikart, G. (2007). *Conservation and the genetics of populations*.

387 Blackwell Publishing: Malden

388

389 Allendorf, F.W., Leary, R.F., Spuell, P. & Wenburg, J.K. (2001). The problems with

390 hybrids: setting conservation guideline. *Trends Ecol. Evol.* **16**, 613-622

391 Bandelt, H.J., Forster, P. & Röhl, A. (1999). Median-joining networks for inferring
392 intraspecific phylogenies. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **16**, 37-48
393

394 Barbanera, F., Negro, J.J., Di Giuseppe, G., Bertoncini, F., Cappelli, F. & Dini, F.
395 (2005). Analysis of the genetic structure of red-legged partridge (*Alectoris rufa*,
396 Galliformes) populations by means of mitochondrial DNA and RAPD markers: a
397 study from central Italy. *Biol. Conserv.* **122**, 275-287
398

399 Barbanera, F., Guerrini, M., Hadjigerou, P., Panayides, P., Sokos, P., Wilkinson, P.,
400 Khan, A.A., Khan, B.Y., Cappelli, F. & Dini, F. (2007). Genetic insight into
401 Mediterranean chukar (*Alectoris chukar*, Galliformes) populations inferred from
402 mitochondrial DNA and RAPD markers. *Genetica* **131**, 287-298
403

404 Barbanera, F., Guerrini, M., Khan, A.A., Panayides, P., Hadjigerou, P., Sokos, C.,
405 Gombobaatar, S., Samadi, S., Khan, B.Y., Tofanelli, S., Paoli, G. & Dini, F. (2009).
406 Human-mediated introgression of exotic chukar (*Alectoris chukar*, Galliformes)
407 genes from East Asia into native Mediterranean partridges. *Biol. Invasions* **11**, 333-
408 348
409

410 Barbanera, F., Pergams, O.R.W., Guerrini, M., Forcina, G., Panayides, P. & Dini, F.
411 (2010). Genetic consequences of intensive management in game birds. *Biol.*
412 *Conserv.* **143**, 1259-1268
413

414 Barilani, M., Bernard-Laurent, A., Mucci, N., Tabarroni, C., Kark, S., Perez Garrido,
415 J.A. & Randi, E. (2007). Hybridisation with introduced chukars (*Alectoris chukar*)
416 threatens the gene pool integrity of native rock (*A. graeca*) and red-legged (*A. rufa*)

417 partridge populations. *Biol. Conserv.* **137**, 57-69

418

419 BirdLife International. (2004). *Birds in Europe: population estimates, trends and*

420 *conservation status*, 12, BirdLife International: Wageningen

421

422 Birkan, M. (1990). *La perdrix rouge*. Brochure technique de l'Office Nationale de la

423 Chasse, 10, Paris

424

425 Birky, C.W., Maruyama, T. & Fuerst, P. (1983). An approach to population and

426 evolutionary genetic theory for genes in mitochondria and chloroplasts, and some

427 results. *Genetics* **103**, 513-527

428

429 Borden, W.C. & Stepien, C.A. (2006). Discordant population genetic structuring of

430 Smallmouth Bass, *Micropterus dolomieu* Lacepède, in Lake Erie based on

431 mitochondrial DNA sequences and nuclear DNA microsatellites. *J. Great Lake Res.*

432 **32**, 242-257

433

434 Cramp, S. & Simmons, K.E.L. (1980). *Handbook of the birds of Europe, the Middle*

435 *East and North Africa*, 2, Oxford University Press: Oxford

436

437 Cristescu, R., Sherwin, W.B., Handasyde, K., Cahill, V. & Cooper, D.W. (2010).

438 Detecting bottlenecks using BOTTLENECK 1.2.02 in wild populations: the

439 importance of the microsatellite structure. *Conserv. Genet.* **11**, 1043-1049

440

441 Erixon, P., Svennblad, B., Britton, T. & Oxelman, B. (2003). Reliability of bayesian

442 probabilities and bootstrap frequencies in phylogenetics. *Syst. Biol.* **52**, 665-673

443 Excoffier, L., Laval, G. & Schneider, S. (2005). Arlequin ver. 3.0: An integrated
444 software package for population genetics data analysis. *Evol. Bioinformatics Online*
445 **1**, 47-50
446

447 Faggio, G., Cart, S. & Jolin, C. (2009). *Bilan des actions sur le Milan royal Milvus*
448 *milvus en Corse en 2009*. AAPNRC/CEN: Bastia, Corsica
449

450 Falchi, A., Paolini, J., Desjobert, J-M., Melis, A., Costa, J. & Varesi, L. (2009).
451 Phylogeography of *Cistus creticus* L. on Corsica and Sardinia inferred by the
452 TRNL-F and RPL32-TRNL sequences of cpDNA. *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.* **52**, 538-
453 543
454

455 Felsenstein, J. (1985). Confidence limits on phylogenies: an approach using the
456 bootstrap. *Evolution* **39**, 783-791
457

458 Frankham, R., Ballou, J.D. & Briscoe, D.A. (2002). *Introduction to conservation*
459 *genetics*. Cambridge University Press: Cambridge
460

461 Gamisans, J. (1991). *La Végétation de la Corse*. Édisud: Aix-en-Provence, France
462

463 Gonzalez, E.G., Castillia, A.M. & Zardoya, R. (2005). Novel polymorphic
464 microsatellites for the red-legged partridge (*Alectoris rufa*) and cross-species
465 amplification in *Alectoris graeca*. *Mol. Ecol. Notes* **5**, 449-451
466

467 Grant, P.R. & Grant, B.R. (2002). Unpredictable evolution in a 30-year study of
468 Darwin's finches. *Science* **296**, 707-711

469 Hasegawa, M., Kishino, H. & Yano, T.A. (1985). Dating of the human–ape splitting by
470 a molecular clock of mitochondrial DNA. *J. Mol. Evol.* **22**, 160-174
471

472 Hillis, D.M. & Bull, J.J. (1993). An empirical test of bootstrapping as a method for
473 assessing confidence in phylogenetic analysis. *Syst. Biol.* **42**, 182-192
474

475 Hochberg, Y. (1988). A sharper Bonferroni procedure for multiple tests of significance.
476 *Biometrika* **75**, 800-802
477

478 Huelsenbeck, J.P. & Ronquist, F. (2001). MrBayes: Bayesian inference of phylogenetic
479 trees. *Bioinformatics* **17**, 754-755
480

481 Kumar, S., Dudley, J., Nei, M. & Tamura, K. (2008). MEGA: A biologist-centric
482 software for evolutionary analysis of DNA and protein sequences. *Brief. Bioinform.*
483 **9**, 299-306
484

485 Librado, P. & Rozas, J. (2009). DnaSP v5: a software for comprehensive analysis of
486 DNA polymorphism data. *Bioinformatics* **25**, 1451-1452
487

488 Madge, S. & McGowan, P. (2002). *Pheasants, partridges and grouse*. A and C Black
489 Ltd: London
490

491 Nylander, J.A.A. (2004). MRMODELTEST, version 2. Program distributed by the
492 author
493

494 Olden, D.J., Poff, N.L., Douglas, M.R., Douglas, E.M. & Fausch, K.D. (2004).

495 Ecological and evolutionary consequences of biotic homogenization. *Trends Ecol.*
496 *Evol.* **19**, 18-24
497
498 Parrot, C. (1910). *Caccabis rufa corsa*. In *Ornithologische Monatsberichte*: 156.
499 Reichenow, A. (Ed.). Verlag von R. Friedlander & Sohn: Berlin
500
501 Pietri, C., Queney, G., Barbanera, F., Ricci, J-C. & Dini, F. (2004). *Premières études*
502 *génétiques sur les perdrix rouges de Corse*. Rapport technique de la Fédération
503 Départementale des Chasseurs de Haute-Corse, 32, Bastia
504
505 Posada, D. & Crandall, K.A. (1998). Modeltest: testing the model of DNA substitution.
506 *Bioinformatics* **14**, 817-818
507
508 Posada, D. & Buckley, T.R. (2004). Model selection and model averaging in
509 phylogenetics: advantages of the AIC and Bayesian approaches over likelihood ratio
510 tests. *Syst. Biol.* **53**, 793-808
511
512 Rambaud, A. & Drummond, A.J. (2007). Tracer v.1.4. Available from:
513 <<http://beast.bio.ed.ac.uk/Tracer/>>.
514
515 Randi, E. (1996). A Mitochondrial Cytochrome-b phylogeny of the *Alectoris* Partridges.
516 *Mol. Phylogenet. Evol.* **2**, 214-227
517
518 Randi, E., Tabarroni, C., Rimondi, S., Lucchini, V. & Sfougaris, A. (2003).
519 Phylogeography of the rock partridge (*Alectoris graeca*). *Mol. Ecol.* **12**, 2201-2214
520

521 Raymond, M. & Rousset, F. (1995). GENEPOP: population genetics software for exact
522 tests and ecumenicism. *J. Hered.* **86**, 248-249
523

524 Reid, W.V. & Miller, K.R. (1989). *Keeping options alive: the scientific basis for*
525 *conserving biodiversity*. World Resources Institute: Washington
526

527 Reille, M., Gamsans, J., de Beaulieu, J-L. & Andrieu, V. (1997). The late glacial at Lac
528 de Creno (Corsica, France): a key site in the western Mediterranean basin. *New*
529 *Phytol.* **135**, 547-449
530

531 Rhymer, J.M. & Simberloff, D. (1996). Extinction by hybridization and introgression.
532 *Ann. Rev. Ecol. Syst.* **27**, 83-109
533

534 Saitou, N. & Nei, M. (1987). The neighbor-joining method: A new method for
535 reconstructing phylogenetic trees. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* **4**, 406-425
536

537 Sevane, N., Cortés, O., García, D., Cañón, J. & Dunner, S. (2010). New single
538 nucleotide polymorphisms in *Alectoris* identified using chicken genome information
539 allow *Alectoris* introgression detection. *Mol. Ecol. Res.* **10**, 205-213
540

541 Short, L.L. (1969). Taxonomic aspects of avian hybridization. *The Auk* **86**, 84-105
542

543 Slatkin, M. (1985). Rare alleles as indicators of gene flow. *Evolution* **39**, 53-65
544

545 Spanò, S. (2010). *La Pernice rossa*. Il Piviere Editore: Gavi, Italia
546

547 Swofford, D.L. (2002). *PAUP*: Phylogenetic Analysis Using Parsimony*. Sinauer
548 Associates: Sunderland, MA
549
550 Swofford, D.L., Olsen, G.J., Waddell, P.J. & Hillis, D.M. (1996). Phylogenetic
551 inference. In *Molecular Systematics*: 407-514. Hillis, D.M., Moritz, C. & Mable,
552 B.K. (Eds.). Sinauer: Sunderland, MA
553
554 Tamura, K. & Nei, M. (1993). Estimation of the number of the nucleotide substitutions
555 in the control region of mitochondrial DNA in humans and chimpanzees. *Mol. Biol.*
556 *Evol.* **10**, 512-526
557
558 Vigne, J.D., Bailon, S. & Cuisin, J. (1997). Biostratigraphy of amphibians, reptiles,
559 birds and mammals in Corsica and the role of man in the Holocene faunal turnover.
560 *Anthropozoologica* **25-26**, 587-604
561
562 Wright, S. (1951). The genetical structure of populations. *Ann. Eugen.* **15**, 323-354
563
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Species	Study area	Population	Samples (<i>n</i>)	Tissue type	mtDNA (<i>n</i>)	STR (<i>n</i>)
<i>A. rufa hispanica</i>	Portugal	Various	4	Liver	4	-
<i>A. rufa hispanica</i>	Spain	Various	16	Liver, feather	16	-
<i>A. rufa intercedens</i>	Spain	Various	32	Liver, feather	32	-
<i>A. rufa rufa</i>	France	Various	24	Feather	24	-
<i>A. rufa rufa</i>	Corsica	Desertu di l'Agriate	16	Liver	15	16
<i>A. rufa rufa</i>	Corsica	Nessa-Felicetu	30	Liver	15	30
<i>A. rufa rufa</i>	Corsica	Vivariu-Venacu	20	Liver	15	20
<i>A. rufa rufa</i>	Corsica	Fium'Orbu-Taravu	31	Liver	15	31
<i>A. rufa rufa</i>	Italy	Various	29	Blood, feather, liver	29	-
Total					165	97

Table 1

$d \pm SE$ (%)	Corsica	<i>A. r. rufa</i>	<i>A. r. intercedens</i>	<i>A. r. hispanica</i>
Corsica	-	-	-	-
<i>A. r. rufa</i>	0.22 ± 0.12	-	-	-
<i>A. r. intercedens</i>	0.24 ± 0.13	0.01 ± 0.01	-	-
<i>A. r. hispanica</i>	0.35 ± 0.14	0.12 ± 0.06	0.09 ± 0.05	-

Table 2

Locus	Repeated motif	Fium'Orbu - Taravu							Nessa - Felicetu				Desertu di l'Agriate				Vivariu - Venacu			
		T _a (°C)	Size range (bp)	A _T	n	Ar	H _O /H _E	P	n	Ar	H _O /H _E	P	n	Ar	H _O /H _E	P	n	Ar	H _O /H _E	P
MCW 104	(TG) ₄	62/55	80 - 126	6	31.0	4.5	0.58/0.61	0.050	30.0	4.7	0.30/0.32	0.346	16.0	2.0	0.25/0.31	0.434	20.0	2.8	0.45/0.42	> 0.99
MCW 118	(TA) ₂ (TATG) ₃ [TA (TATG) ₂] ₂ (TA) ₃ (TATG)	60/55	143 - 155	1	31.0	1.0	Mono.	-	30.0	1.0	Mono.	-	16.0	1.0	Mono.	-	20.0	1.0	Mono.	-
MCW 121	(TG) ₈	58/55	182 - 200	4	31.0	2.9	0.64/0.58	0.097	29.0	2.9	0.31/0.28	> 0.99	16.0	3.0	0.56/0.63	0.630	20.0	3.9	0.65/0.65	0.413
MCW 146	(TG) ₁₁	62/60	148 - 168	5	31.0	3.0	0.16/0.63	< 0.001*	30.0	2.0	0.50/0.51	> 0.99	16.0	2.0	0.56/0.47	0.590	20.0	3.9	0.35/0.55	0.039
MCW 276	(TG) ₄	60/55	185 - 199	3	31.0	2.5	0.16/0.21	0.317	29.0	2.0	0.34/0.33	> 0.99	16.0	2.0	0.50/0.48	> 0.99	20.0	2.0	0.15/0.29	0.067
MCW 280	(AT) ₈	60/55	174 - 180	3	30.0	2.0	0.40/0.49	0.456	29.0	2.8	0.45/0.45	0.828	16.0	2.0	0.31/0.51	0.150	16.0	2.0	0.31/0.49	0.292
Aru 1.23	(TG) ₁₃	62/55	173 - 187	3	31.0	2.5	0.51/0.44	0.164	30.0	2.8	0.40/0.44	0.680	16.0	2.0	0.37/0.44	0.591	20.0	2.0	0.45/0.48	> 0.99
Aru 1.27	(AT) ₁₄	60/55	172 - 200	5	31.0	3.9	0.26/0.51	0.002*	30.0	4.8	0.47/0.67	0.005*	16.0	4.0	0.37/0.61	0.029	20.0	3.7	0.55/0.45	0.825
All loci				30	30.9	2.8	0.39/0.50	< 0.001*	29.6	2.9	0.40/0.43	0.465	16.0	2.2	0.42/0.49	0.341	19.5	2.6	0.42/0.48	0.285

Table 3

N_{em} / F_{ST}	Fium'Orbu-Taravu	Nessa-Felicetu	Desertu di l'Agriate	Vivariu-Venacu	Carbuccia
Fium'Orbu-Taravu	-	1.6	1.8	1.7	1.0
Nessa-Felicetu	0.070**	-	4.2	3.3	2.0
Desertu di l'Agriate	0.038*	0.048*	-	3.7	1.5
Vivariu-Venacu	0.020	0.049**	0.005	-	1.4
Carbuccia	0.14**	0.22**	0.17**	0.21**	-

Table 4

573 **Figures and Tables captions**

574

575 **Fig. 1.** Map showing sampling localities of red-legged partridges in the Iberian
576 Peninsula, France, Italy and Corsica. The distribution range of each *A. rufa* subspecies
577 is marked out by the uninterrupted lines. Upper left corner: the studied Corsican
578 populations are showed: DA, Desertu di l'Agriate; NF, Nessa-Felicetu; VV, Vivariu-
579 Venacu; FT, Fium'Orbu-Taravu. The white circle marks out the only *A. rufa* partridge
580 island farm (Carbuccia). The thick dotted line shows the depression connecting DA and
581 VV areas and harbouring Ostriconi (1), Golo (2) and Tavignano (3) river valleys.

582

583 **Fig. 2.** NJ tree computed by PAUP* for the aligned *A. rufa* haplotypes using *A. graeca* as
584 outgroup (Barbanera *et al.*, 2009). The MP and Bayesian methods produced
585 reconstructions overlapping with that obtained by NJ. Statistic support was reported
586 only at significant internodes: above, left side: bootstrap percentage values computed in
587 the NJ; above, right side: bootstrap percentage values computed in the MP; below:
588 posterior probability values computed in the Bayesian analysis. The number of
589 specimens and their geographic occurrence are indicated for each haplotype; *:
590 internodes without significant statistic support (see Materials and methods). Inset:
591 haplotype network as computed with NETWORK. A scale to infer the number of
592 haplotypes for each pie is provided together with a length bar to compute the number of
593 mutational changes. Ibe, Iberian Peninsula; Fra, France (mainland); Co, Corsica; Ita,
594 Italy.

595

596 **Fig. 3.** The PCA performed using the pairwise F_{ST} distances. PCAs were produced using

597 either (white circles) only five STR loci (including Carbuccia farm: see Materials and
598 methods) or (black circles) the entire set of STR loci (wild populations of this study).

599

600 **Table 1.** Red-legged partridge sampling details are given together with the number of
601 specimens either mtDNA or STR genotyped (Fig. 1). Iberian Peninsula samples were
602 assigned to each morphological subspecies on the basis of their geographic origin
603 according to Madge & McGowan (2002).

604

605 **Table 2.** Average genetic distance values ($d \pm SE$, %) computed between Corsica ($n =$
606 60) and each morphological *A. rufa* subspecies (*A. r. rufa*, $n = 53$; *A. r. intercedens*, $n =$
607 32; *A. r. hispanica*, $n = 20$; Table 1).

608

609 **Table 3.** STR loci and variability of Corsican *A. rufa*. Legend: T_a ($^{\circ}C$), for the 1st/2nd
610 annealing temperatures in the touch-down PCR; A_T , total number of alleles for each
611 locus; n , sample size; A_r , allelic richness; H_O , observed heterozygosity; H_E , expected
612 heterozygosity; P , probability value for the HWE test. Mono., monomorphic locus; *:
613 significant departure from HWE after application of Bonferroni correction ($\alpha = 0.05$, α'
614 $= \alpha/8 = 0.006$).

615

616 **Table 4.** The effective number of migrants per generation ($N_e m$: above the diagonal) and
617 the F_{ST} pairwise distance values (below the diagonal) as computed among all pairs of
618 wild Corsican populations (entire set of STR loci) and between these latter and the
619 Carbuccia farm population (five STR loci: see Materials and Methods). *, $P < 0.05$; **,
620 $P < 0.001$; others, $P > 0.05$.